

Evaluating how teachers can match methodology to learner needs and the process of the strengths and weaknesses of teaching methodologies/philosophies, including:

- **Behaviorism**
- **Audio-lingualism**
- **The 'Natural Way'**
- **Humanistic Approaches**

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Teaching language by using methodology may be interesting for learners and for teachers too. In this case, teacher should evaluate students' age, interest as well as faculty. It sometimes depends on educational philosophy. However, teaching methodology does not look like an educational philosophy, despite relating it with methodology. The philosophy is a way that teacher opts for pointing to why she believes students can learn well a new material or topic the ways in that students and teachers should interact during the lesson. Philosophy often impacts the options that teaching methodology she chooses to use.

Teachers commonly refer to their preferred teaching methods and philosophies together. While a numerous methodologies can be utilized by a teacher. A common and conventional teaching method is often chosen by teachers as lecturing or explaining. Teacher provides the information to the students at the beginning and then students are expected to understand the topic. There are some teachers that they focus on the significance of the learners' learning process such as group work, group discussion, small group discussion, and pair work. As a result, they can learn to be sociable and try to communicate with classmates. Therefore they are encouraged to take responsibility for their education and are active participants in the learning process. Moreover, it will increase discipline in the classroom to achieve basic curriculum objectives.

There are some learning methods such as behaviorism, audio-lingual, the natural way and humanistic that they may consist of advantages or disadvantages.

Behaviorism is a method that looks at observable actions of students and marks if they are learning effectively. On the one hand, they are always given feedback which tells them whether they are doing it correctly or not. They would be checked by test, task, homework. On the other hand, there are also disadvantages that the approach disregards student identity and individuality. Furthermore, it studies actions of body rather than that of the brain thus is considered ineffective at assessing real learning.

While in audio-lingual approach students are taught listening and speaking skills, it means the instructor presents the right model of a sentence and then students will repeat it. Students learn without understanding fully. However, they are not very good at vocabulary. Thus students are likely to come across problems of reading and writing skills. In addition to this, that it is a teacher dominated method.

In natural way students feel themselves energetic to play games, activities, problem-solving activities that can help them to communicate much more than the teacher. However, it does not pay attention to the grammar. This method is useful for young learners not for the students of senior high school. Nowadays, it is in the process because of being easy to apply and quite simple to understand. So teachers can relate it with other methods.

Humanistic learning method is a method of a student-centered learning. It focuses on human beings rather than supernatural or divine insight. It also pays attention to the idea that children are good at the cores the education focus on rational ways to teach the "whole" child. This approach engages social skills, artistic skills, practical skills. Teacher helps students develop learning skills and motivate. Nowadays all approaches are mixed up and used in a correct way by teacher and create a mixed method regarding to students level of knowledge, and needs.

To be a good teacher is more difficult than we thought. Because a professional instructor should be sophisticated in creating group opportunities to help students observe. The teacher needs to create a friendly, learning environment in a classroom that students can enjoy during the lesson. In this way, a lot of methods can be helpful for teachers. It would be better if the teacher used a wide range of methods together for achieving objectives.

Firstly, the teacher needs to determine which method is effective for his students. A perfect teacher should be an optimist and tries to present a new theme with grammar rules at the beginning of the lesson. After giving examples students would be checked by multiple choice questions or wheels game, give me a five activity for giving feedback. It is crucial to give feedback to every student to improve their knowledge and speaking skills. It will be also a useful listening exercise. During these tasks, teachers should explain the correct meaning of the words by giving a definition or guessing in the context. While in grammar the students can imitate the teacher by repeating the rules. In this process, he teaches behaviorism with an audio-lingual approach. But students want to get more knowledge as soon as possible. So they need to be taught by cramming or playing games, and funny activities to avoid being bored. In the activities, students are at the center of the process, while teachers are second-centered persons. They do activities and acquire skills without knowing the right rules. If the teacher matches the approaches in a humanistic way, it will be a perfect lesson. Because of evaluation effectively by many teachers around the world. Not only can teachers teach the students but also learn their outlook, and try to adapt them.

Modern teachers functions may change during the lesson process, for instance if she begins the lesson she tries to be a facilitator to her learners. While during the activities she is accustomed to showing independent participant. Moreover , she can check the homework as needs analyst or works like group process manager.

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